
Repetition of Antiquity at the Peak of Modernity as Phenomenological Problem

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Abstract: One of the distinctive features of Modernity is that Modernity represents in itself a problem for philosophers, who have called themselves modern. If this is true for philosophers proud to be modern such as Descartes, Kant or Hegel, this is even truer for those thinkers, who see in Modernity the cause of the contemporary Western cultural crisis. The latter is the case of Jacob Klein, whose reflection will be the subject-matter of the present work. In particular, what I want to point out is: a) the role of the idea of a “natural” way of dealing with the world in Klein’s first masterpiece *Greek Mathematical Thought and the Origins of Algebra*, and b) its origin in Edmund Husserl’s and Martin Heidegger’s phenomenological thought. My ground thesis is that there is a strong connection between Klein’s analysis of Modernity and the phenomenological tradition.

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1. Husserl’s Phenomenology and the natural world¹

In order for a philosophical analysis to be called phenomenological, it has not to hide experience with concepts. Particularly famous is Husserl’s formula *zu den Sachen selbst!*² taken from the *Introduction* to the *Logical Investigations*. Unfortunately this expression has been totally misunderstood. It has been interpreted by scholars as a plea for absolute idealism that, attempting to open consciousness to the world, closes the world into consciousness. In order to avoid such a misleading, but in any case so commonly accepted, interpretation, I think we had better read another passage if we want to understand what phenomenology is. In the *Preface* to the *Logical Investigations*, in a little biographical sketch, Husserl explains how and why he came to be interested in the logic: «... sah ich mich in immer steigendem Maße zu allgemeinen kritischen Reflexionen über das Wesen der Logik und zumal über das Verhältnis zwischen der Subjektivität des Erkennens und der Objektivität des Erkenntnisinhaltes gedrängt»³. These words are at the very beginning of Husserl’s first masterpiece, in the only passage in the whole text in which Husserl speaks of himself. Actually Husserl is defining here the programme and the aim of his work, that I could resume as: how is it possible that from subjective representations we gain knowledge of objects, such as mathematics and science in general, totally inde-

pendent from us? This question lies at the very heart of *Logical Investigations*, determining their structure as well as their contents. Husserl’s great discovery at the end of 19th century was not phenomenology, but the independence of the laws of logic from the process of knowledge acquisition. The *Prolegomena zu einer reinen Logik* are in this sense the most important part of the work, since in them Husserl tries to show – against psychologism – that objective truths are possible and necessary in every epistemological strategy. Phenomenology arose from Husserl’s concern with the issue of proving our access to objective truths. Far from being the source of his criticism of psychologism, it was rather its consequence. Only after the publication of *Logical Investigations* (more or less from 1904) Husserl realized that he had discovered a new way of dealing with consciousness: from that moment on, phenomenology takes the central role that will keep till the *Crisis of European Science*.

The central change in Husserl’s thought follows a change in his understanding of the meaning of experience. This concept assumes its real phenomenological aspect in the 1907 lectures on constitution of space. In that context, Husserl undertakes a criticism of another way of understanding experience: that of Neo-kantians⁴. Cohen in particular had proposed a notion of experience based on the possibility to comprehend the perceptual given inside scientific laws. From the Neo-Kantian point of view, the perceptual multiplicity of the world cannot be intended as an object unless it is ordered through scientific categories, i.e. through reason in its historical objectivity. Representations have to be part of a conceptual construction and only insofar as they are constructed by concepts they could be objects for us. Construction is not a casual word here. It derives specifically from Cohen’s interpretation of Kant’s *Critique of pure Reason*. In fact in the second edition of his *Kant’s Theory of Experience*, Cohen uses construction to refer to every possible activity of transcendental thought. In so doing, he makes construction the peculiar feature of criticism and, consequently, of all modern philosophy⁵.

Criticizing Neo-kantians means for Husserl criticizing this notion of construction as the source of objectivity⁶. According to Husserl, the weak point in the Neo-Kantian epistemological theory is the idea that the given needs a concept in order to be considered an object. This stems from the fact that Neo-Kantians equate things with objects, without noticing that in order to be an object a thing has to undergo an extremely complicated process of con-

stitution. Since experience has in itself the conditions for its own constitution sense data are not just raw material for a synthetizing concept. The Neo-Kantian account remains bound to the everyday account of the world, according to which our environment is full of things. This presupposition, that of presupposing the existence of the world as a world of things, is what Husserl calls from the first volume of the *Ideas for a Pure Phenomenology and Phenomenological Philosophy* on natural attitude⁷. Natural attitude is the basic component of our world. Our everyday life is grounded in the unmade decision of trusting the existence of the world, i.e. that the world and the objects in it have existence independently from any consciousness whatsoever. Natural attitude makes it possible for us to live a life; more radically, it is the very basis of any activity in the world.

Particularly important in this sense is the fact that every scientist has the natural attitude as his way of life. But that is not all about science. In an extremely interesting chapter of the second volume of his *Ideas*, Husserl points out that within natural attitude there are two main possibilities of dealing with the world: the personalistic and the naturalistic attitude⁸. I am interested in the latter. Naturalistic attitude is that of a scientist that presupposes nature as a separate field of reality, that we can know through mathematical formula and physical laws. At every moment, a scientist must presuppose not only the existence of a world of things, but a specific kind of reality: a mathematized nature. Both natural and naturalistic attitude share the same approach to reality: they do not look directly at experience, but projects concepts on it, and, in so doing, they remain always alone with themselves. Natural or naturalistic thought is a thinking closed in its products, according to which truth is just what thought is able to construct. Modern tradition is essentially committed to this tantalizing predicament: a mythology of construction which can never grasp the ultimate layer of immediate experience. Grasping such layer is the aim of phenomenology.

Overcoming natural attitude means in this sense overcoming Modernity as a whole. Phenomenology must put aside the basic presupposition of modern tradition, i.e. leave the presupposition of the existence of a world of things as starting point of philosophical reflection. Husserl's methodological strategy is well-known and it consists in transcendental reduction. This is an imaginative work of the philosopher⁹, in order to put aside all the concepts normally covering experience "as a dress", as Husserl would say¹⁰. When Husserl speaks of bracketing the objects what he means is just a process, through which our presupposition of the existence of the world becomes no longer important for us. We look at the world as if its existence would have no importance for us, and in so doing we discover the reign of transcendental subjectivity. This is the layer of the original self-constitution of the object. It is important to properly understand what Husserl means with the notion of "self-constituted object". Insofar as they are *self-constituted*, they have in themselves the figurative structure that ensures their unity and recognition and insofar as they are *self-constituted*, they need the recognition of the sense-giving attention of a consciousness. Husserl's rigorous science aims at describing the ways in which the processes of self-

constitution of the objects take place; consequently, it can grasp a layer of experience totally prelogical and so not conceptual.

2. Heidegger and the Greek world as natural world

Heidegger's first philosophical interest was not the problem of being, but the epistemological question about the reality of the world, that is, the quarrel between idealism and realism. This is the background of Heidegger's early thought and the basis for his early phenomenological conception of the relation between experience and concept. The discovery of Husserl's phenomenology reveals to Heidegger the impossibility of solving the problem of the existence of the world in Neo-Kantian terms. Thanks to phenomenology Heidegger understands that the idealism-realism problem is not a real problem. This means that it is not a problem born in the concreteness of experience, but a question raised by the modern world and therefore inevitably bound to the modern epistemic forms of knowledge: realism and idealism are products of Galilei's intellectual revolution in the XVII century¹¹. Mathematical physics determines each and every philosophical approach grown up in modernity. This means that every approach (including Husserl's phenomenological method) is determined by modern scientific conceptuality, and therefore it is what Heidegger calls *das Theoretische*. But if all modern philosophy is a product of the modern scientific world, how is it possible to realize a real phenomenology of experience, i.e. a consideration of the world able to grasp the *Vortheoretische*, that establishes the possibility of every conceptual approach? Husserl's answer to that problem was transcendental reduction, but from Heidegger's point of view transcendental reduction is not a way free from modern prejudices. Actually, through reduction Husserl aims to grasp the *Urfaktizität* of consciousness, i.e. the phenomena in their *Selbstgebung*. So *Gegebenheit* is the pillar of every strategy within the Husserlian method, but – as Heidegger notices – the fact that something is given to a consciousness implicitly presupposes the distinction between subject and object, which is a typical modern approach to epistemological questions. But if phenomenological ontology has to make no use of transcendental reduction, which way is left open to Heidegger in order to grasp Being in its authenticity? In order to answer this question I have to say something more about Husserl.

As is well-known, the subject-matter of the first logical investigation is a phenomenological account of the relation between sign and its meaning. Before dealing with meaningful language, Husserl draws an all-important distinction between *Ausdruck*, expression, and *Anzeige*, indication. The difference is that only in the first case the sign has a meaning in a proper sense. If I say "book" these four letters refer to a sense that is their proper sense, while I presuppose a conceptual link between the sign and its meaning. In opposition to expression, indication has not a proper meaning. What is peculiar about an indication is its capacity to show an object without the help of a conceptual framework. In the relation between a flag and a nation there is no concept, but an immediate reference.

While Husserl was interested in expression, indication gains a central methodological role in Heidegger's early writings in the form of what Heidegger calls *formale Anzeige*. Formal indication makes it possible to refer to experience through a linguistic structure which has nothing to do with concepts and consequently with construction¹². A peculiar feature of formal indication is worth noting: it must refer directly to experience. Otherwise it would not be what it is, i.e. what can bring us in contact with the original experience of being-in-the-world. Therefore no concept elaborated by Modern philosophy can be used as formal indication leading to immediacy. On this point Heidegger follows Natorp's interpretation of the history of philosophy, according to which the peculiar feature of modernity is the absolute sovereignty of construction over every other form of objectivity. From a neokantian point of view this is the great theoretical achievement of Modernity over Antiquity; on the contrary, Heidegger inverts the perspective. Construction is precisely the problem of modernity that must be overcome, and only ancient wisdom offers us such a possibility. As Heidegger writes in a 1921 lecture:

Das Echte ist immer neu, weil das Alte immer in irgendeinem Sinne für uns unecht geworden ist. - Ich finde das Echte nur, sofern das Alte mir dabei ist, eine Strecke weit in Rückgang von ihm mitgeht. Es ist als Vollzugsmäßiges Motiv im Philosophieren immer irgendwie in existentieller Notwendigkeit da¹³.

Modern scientific revolution built itself on an already present cultural paradigm, that of Greek science. Being modern, we understand science as a theoretical construction through concepts. In opposition to modern, the ancients understood the world in its immediacy. In this sense Plato's or Aristotle's comprehension of the world was founded immediately in a direct world-experience; this is the reason why their texts pave the way for discovering the authenticity of original being. Greek philosophy originates from an original and non-conceptual look at the world in its worldliness and therefore it is *natural*. In Heidegger's early reflections the word natural has a great importance, because it justifies the attention Heidegger devotes to Plato and Aristotle, but its meaning is far from being clear. What is clear is that natural is the direct opposite to construction as the following passages states: «So wie nun das erste εἶδος der τέχνη bzw. die ποιήσις, einen Ausblick auf das Verständnis von οὐσία gewährte und uns die Gelegenheit gab, den natürlichen – konstruktionsfreien – Sinn von Sein bei den Griechen herauszuheben, [...]»¹⁴.

But the real problem is: which place is actually that of Greek natural consciousness in the construction of metaphysics, so which kind of interpretation of being did the Greeks have? Explaining Aristotle's conception of being, Heidegger says: «Der fundamentale Wert dieser Analysen liegt darin, daß *Aristoteles gegenüber irgendwelchen theoretischen Konstruktionen ausgegangen ist von dem, was man zunächst sieht*»¹⁵. First of all it must be said that the Greeks are always seen in opposition to the moderns and so if Heidegger speaks positively about them is always in order to bring to light modern conceptual roots. But that does not mean that Greeks are the right side of history and they are not, precisely because of their im-

mediate naturalty. Our surrounding world is a world of objects and their naturalty is to be used by human beings. Therefore, man naturally looks at the world as a world of objects to be used. An object can be used only if it becomes an instrument and it can be understood as such if and only if it is present. The Greek world is the world of daily life experience, and that's why it is called natural. It is exactly what Husserl would have called the natural attitude toward the world and existence. We saw that Husserl intended with naturalty an attitude toward reality that presupposes the presence of reality as being independent from consciousness. Like the Husserlian natural attitude, Heidegger's greek natural consciousness takes the world for granted as a presence and it is the ground for every philosophical position in Antiquity. In this sense it could be said that Heidegger uses Husserl's transcendental concepts as a set of historical descriptive categories.

The Greek natural world is the basic level of Greek daily life experience and Greek philosophy tries again and again to overcome this natural attitude, but in so doing it remains bound inevitably to the naturalty of its starting point. More specifically if the natural world of Greeks sees beings as present instruments for our daily life, Greek philosophy interprets being as presence. This justifies the aim of Heidegger's phenomenological strategy in interpreting Greek texts. What he is interested in is not a reconstruction of the Greek mind (as could be the case with Jaeger's work on Aristotle's development), but the discovery *through* Greek concepts used as formal indication of the basic categories of existence. If Greeks are not the original itself, they are the door to originality.

3. Klein and Heidegger

It seems trivial to say that there is a relation between Heidegger's phenomenology and Jacob Klein's critique of modern symbolic mathematics, but actually we have no sure evidence about this matter. It is really difficult to determine which among Heidegger's lectures Klein actually attended to and so, even if a debt with Heidegger is evident, it is really complicated to state it historically and conceptually. What we can take for granted is that Klein attended to Heidegger's lectures in 1924, in particular the course about the basic concepts of aristotelian philosophy¹⁶. Klein studied at Marburg-University until 1924, when he came back to Berlin. But he continued to attend lectures in Marburg until the end of twenties. I assume it to be very probable that Klein was in Heidegger's classroom until 1927-28. In my opinion what can be affirmed about the Heidegger-Klein relationship is that Heidegger taught Klein how to read a greek text without modern prejudices against it. First of all this means that we have to find evidence that Klein was attracted by Heidegger's approach to ancient philosophy and that Heideggerian phenomenology is the point of view from which Klein learns to see the Greeks.

As far as I can see, we have three main statements about this point. The first is by Klein himself. In a letter to Strauss, Klein says:

Du wirst wahrscheinlich fragen: aber die Arbeit [*Greek Mathematical Thought and the Origin of Algebra*] war doch schon

vor einem Jahr fertig? Ja und nein. Damals war der ganze antike Teil schon *vorhanden*, der in sich ein abgeschlossenes Ganze darstellte. Inzwischen ist das 16. Jahrh. hinzugekommen. Und damit erst der Sinn des Ganzen¹⁷.

This statement says just that the first part of *Greek Mathematical Thought and the Origins of Algebra* was the first to have been written, but the word *vorhanden* leaves open the possibility that its content has roots in Klein's first reflection about the history of mathematics.

The second evidence I want to examine is a passage from an unpublished interview to Klein's wife, where she says:

Q [W. Allenbrook]: He must have been doing all the reading and work for the *The Origins of Algebra* all during the late '20's.

Dodo [Klein's wife]: Yes. That was the result since he entered ...¹⁸

Heidegger's most famous lectures about greek philosophy in Marburg were delivered from 1924 to 1927. If Klein began to write his work at the end of twenties, this was after having attended Heidegger's lectures. But the problem now is to show why Klein's interest in Greek philosophy is bound to Heidegger's lectures. On this point Strauss' statement about Klein is decisive: «Klein was more attracted by the Aristotle brought to light and life by Heidegger than by Heidegger's own philosophy»¹⁹. I think that this statement by Strauss makes it very probable that Heidegger's lectures on Aristotle are the basis for Klein's analysis of Greek thought. But why should a young and brilliant student find it interesting to speak about Aristotle or Greek in general? Again it is Strauss who can give us answer to this question:

Klein alone saw why Heidegger is truly important: by uprooting and not simply rejecting the tradition of philosophy, he made it possible for the first time after many centuries – one hesitates to say how many – to see the roots of the tradition as they are and thus perhaps to know, what so many merely believe, that those are the only natural and healthy roots ... Above all, his intention was to uproot Aristotle: he thus was compelled to disinter the roots, to bring them to light, to look at them with wonder²⁰.

Obviously this is Strauss' interpretation of Klein's debt to Heidegger, but I think we can trust it and I want to give a particularly eloquent example of the direct connection between Heidegger's lectures on greek philosophy and Klein's investigation on greek mathematics. In an extraordinarily interesting passage of his lectures about Plato's *Sophist*, delivered in 1925, Heidegger gives a brief account of what Greek thought and in particular Aristotle understood with ἀριθμός:

Das ὅλον im Sinne des Umgreifenden und Zusammenhängenden, sofern es *nach seinem Wieviel betrachtet* wird, ist [...] ein πᾶν, ein Gesamt, eine Allheit. [...] Die letzte Bestimmung des πᾶν ist die auch für die Zahl in Anspruch genommen wird: καὶ ἀριθμός πᾶν μὲν λέγεται, ὅλος δ' ἀριθμός οὐ λέγεται [...]. Der ἀριθμός, das Gezählte, die Summe, wird πᾶν, Gesamt, genannt, nicht aber ὅλον, Ganzes²¹.

Heidegger's interpretation of the Greek concept of number is very clear: number is the product of an addition and

the sum is derived from the process of numbering. Now, one of the most peculiar theses of Klein's interpretation of Greek mathematics is surely his interpretation of the ancient concept of number and – I would say – this is the very heart of his work. He says:

The fundamental phenomenon which we should never lose sight of in determining the meaning of *arithmos* (ἀριθμός) is counting, or more exactly, the *counting-off*, of some number of things. [...] The word which is pronounced last in counting off or numbering, gives the "*counting-number*", the *arithmos* of the things involved. [...] Thus the *arithmos* indicates in each case a *definite number of definite things*²².

In opposition to the modern number, which is a symbol used just for referring to the concept of general quantity, the ancient *arithmos* refers immediately to the subjective operation of numbering a set of things. Heidegger stated that the Greek number is a *Gezählte*, i.e. the numbered of numbering, and Klein also sees the ancient concept of number as totally dependent from the operation of counting.

4. Nature and History in Klein

The origin of *arithmos* from the process of counting is a good example to explain what Klein intends when he speaks about the naturality of Greek science²³. The ancient concept of number born from an original non-scientific experience of the world. The central aim of Greek philosophy is to demonstrate the insufficiency and the inadequacy of the δόξα, of the human natural way of being in the world and with others. Scientific and philosophical concepts stem from a perpetual critique against the daily life of men, but – in so doing – Greek concepts remain inside that natural perspective they wanted to criticize. In this horizon Klein shows the importance of the concept of ἀριθμός for the Greek science. It is the basic concept of every way of finding an order in the world. The Pythagoreans discover the number as the ontological principle of being and make it part and origin of ontology. But if we say that a particular kind of quantity is the principle of things, it is necessary to say that things are in a numerical relations with themselves. Ontology of numbers permits Pythagorean and Plato to discover the necessary relation between good, number and being. Something is just because it is countable; something is countable just because it stays in a numerical relation with other things and this relationship is well ordered; again something is good if it is part of being, it is countable and it stays with other things in a numerical relation. From the Greek point of view, mathematics, ethics and ontology speak about the same thing: *the principles of a well-ordered world*.

In opposition to Antiquity, Modernity is no longer a continuous critique to the world of daily life experience, but against Greek and Medieval science. That means that the bases of modern cultural system are not in the world, but in another cultural system. This relation to a previous cultural system could be intended in two different ways. First of all modern science could not exist without its critique against medieval science. Anyone who reads Des-

cartes, Bacon, Galilei could find unending pages spent criticising scholastic knowledge and – I would say – this is the very core of their own arguments in favour of new science. I mean: modern science affirms itself just because medieval science could no longer solve problems and therefore the new science was born from a critical attitude towards the old one. The second kind of relationship is that with ancient science. The critique against scholasticism had a very brilliant argument in saying that medieval science had hidden the true science of antiquity. The moderns take themselves as the renewers of ancient wisdom, but – in so doing – they deeply modify the ancient comprehension of mathematics, of science in general and consequently of the world. When Viète thinks of renewing Diophantus’ technique to resolve equations, instead of following Diophantus, who proposes just particular solutions for particular equations, he invents a general method able to *non nullum problema solve*, i.e. able not to leave problems unsolved. This deep change is founded in the passage from the ἀριθμός to the modern concept of number. In opposition to the former, the letter is no more an ontological property of a definite amount of things, but a symbol referring to the general concept of quantity. When I write “x” in an equation, I mean that the value of that “x” could be any possible number, so what I refer to, is no more a definite quantity, but the abstract and general concept of quantity. The number has nothing more to do with a way of being, but it is transformed in an operational function of a symbol inside a general framework of axioms. For although moderns understand themselves as the real renewers of antiquity, they do not notice this great difference and this is the most peculiar mark of modern science. Because of this, the new science of Galilei and Descartes understands itself as natural and thinks of its products as an ontological basis of reality, but – as many moderns have said – there is no longer a place for ontology in the modern world.

Klein’s analysis of history points out three main steps (the world of daily life experience, Greek science as natural comprehension and modern symbolic mathematics) that are really similar to Heidegger’s organization of phenomenological history as corruption from the ancient natural understanding to the modern construction and, in my opinion, this common account of a solution to the problem of the relationship between antiquity and modernity is evidence of the fact that Klein has the same problem in common with phenomenological tradition. Husserl’s, Heidegger’s and Klein’s common problem was that of avoiding the resolution of reality and values in products of individual prejudices. Natural experience is not something, that can be destroyed in subjective representations, but is common to every man and so offers the same basic phenomena. From Klein’s point of view phenomenology is the only possibility in order to dismiss modern prejudices, according to which there are no common values, no common experience, no universal structure. Historicism resolves the humanity of man in his history and this destroys every possibility of something in common between us and our ancient roots. Escaping from psychologism Husserl discovers a new possibility of seeing the world, Heidegger shows how this same possibility can be used in order to uproot our modern understanding of the world and Klein does exactly the same.

The great differences between Husserl, Heidegger and Klein is neither the problem nor the methodical presuppositions, but the way of solution. Husserl’s reply to psychologism is transcendental phenomenology and its account of a pure experience given in phenomenological reduction. Heidegger opposes Husserl and historicism the possibility to obtain the existential categories of being from Greek philosophy. And Klein? What about Klein’s solution? It may be doubted there is a really coherent solution to this problem in Klein’s writings, but I think that Klein had one. The peculiarity of Greek thought was – according to Klein – the conjunction between good, order, number and being. This conjunction was founded on the possibility of giving an ontology of the natural world. In this sense the peculiar feature of modernity is the impossibility of furnishing an ontology²⁴ and without ontology the world is just a plurality of events determined by scientific laws²⁵. The modern universe is no more a κόσμος and a τάξις, but a regular sequence of temporal and spatial phenomena in causal relation to one other. Having said this, we can understand that repetition of antiquity in Klein’s thought means a renewing of ontology and the discovery of a new κόσμος. This does not mean that we have to rewrite platonic dialogues. This would be impossible. The natural world is totally lost for the modern, for us²⁶. But if we cannot build an ontology, how can we “repeat antiquity”? Is it possible to have an ontology without being? Klein answers in a very important letter to Gerhard Krüger:

However, while on the one hand methodical progress causes the ordered world to dissolve itself, unawares a *new* “world”, the *historical world* builds up itself – within the categories of this very methodic-systematic thought. Self-knowledge becomes possible only in a historical manner – as the attempt, pushed further and further, to suppress self-alienation. [...] The decisive character of the modern “historical consciousness” is the “wordliness” of the history meant by this consciousness. In Hegel the sameness of the *world* of the Spirit and of the history of the Spirit incorporates itself immediately²⁷.

History is the only possibility to bring the roots of human culture to new life. In fact, modern thought has always to do with its concepts and never with the world. Such concepts cannot have a being in the sense of an objective being, i.e. an existence independent from the process of their generation. Their way of being corresponds to the way of their genesis as historical construction. In this sense if we want to know the *nature* of the modern world, i.e. of modern conceptuality, we have to write its history. In so doing, history is our only possibility of giving new life to ontology, but in a really different manner: an ontology without being.

Notes

¹ I wish to express my gratitude to Roberto Gronda, Lorenzo Serini and Susan Owen for checking the final version of my English text.

² Literally this expression sounds: “Wir wollen auf die “Sachen selbst” zurückgehen”, see E. Husserl, *Gesammelte Werke* (from now on Hua.), Martinus Nijhoff (than Kluwer), Den Haag (than Boston), Bd. XIX/I, 10.

³ Hua. XVIII, 7. My emphasis.

⁴ See the *Introduction to Thing and space*, Hua. XVI, 4.

- ⁵ See M. Ferrari, *Il giovane Cassirer e la scuola di Marburgo*, Franco Angeli, Milano, 1988.
- ⁶ See I. Kern, *Husserl und Kant, Eine Untersuchung über Husserls Verhältnis zu Kant und zum Neukantianismus*, Martinus Nijhoff, Den Haag, 1964;
- ⁷ See Hua. III /I, 10-13.
- ⁸ See Hua. IV, 203.
- ⁹ On this topic see P. Ricoeur, *A l'école de la Phénoménologie*, Vrin, Paris, 1993.
- ¹⁰ See E. Husserl, *Erfahrung und Urteil*, hrsg. von L. Landgrebe, Meiner Verlag, Hamburg, 1999 (first edition: Academica, Prague, 1939), p. 42.
- ¹¹ See M. Heidegger, *Gesamtausgabe* (from now on GA), Vittorio Klostermann, Frankfurt am Main, Bd. LVI-VII, 82-84.
- ¹² See *Phenomenology of Religious Life*, GA LX, 55: «Den methodischen Gebrauch eines Sinnes, der leitend wird für die Phänomenologische Explication, nennen wir 'formale Anzeige'. Was der formal anzeigende Sinn in sich trägt, daraufhin werden die Phänomene angesehen».
- ¹³ GA LIX, 29.
- ¹⁴ GA XIX, 303.
- ¹⁵ GA XIX, 113.
- ¹⁶ Klein mentions Heidegger's lectures on Aristotle in his essay *Aristotle, an introduction*, in J. Klein, *Lectures and Essays* (from now on LE), edited by R.B. Williamson and E. Zuckerman, St John's College Press, Annapolis, 1985, p. 171.
- ¹⁷ L. Strauss, *Gesammelte Schriften*, hrsg von H. Meier, Metzlersche J.B. Verlag, Berlin, 2013, Bd. III, p. 499.
- ¹⁸ I am really thankful to prof. B. Hopkins of Seattle University, who gave me the opportunity to read this interview. This quotation comes from page 14.
- ¹⁹ L. Strauss in *Jewish Philosophy and the Crisis of Modernity: Essays and Lectures in Modern Jewish Thought*, ed. by K.H. Green, State University of New York Press, Albany, 1997, p. 562, quoted in R. Velkley, *Heidegger, Strauss, and the Premises of Philosophy*, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago and London, 2011, p. 6.
- ²⁰ L. Strauss, *An Unspoken Prologue to a Public Lecture to Saint John's*, in *Interpretation*, 7 (3), 1978, p. 2.
- ²¹ GA XIX, 81-2.
- ²² J. Klein, *Greek Mathematical Thought and the Origins of Algebra* (from now on GMOA), translated by E. Brann, Dover publications, New-York, 1992, p. 46.
- ²³ In general see on this topic B. Hopkins, *The Origin of the Logic of Symbolic Mathematics: Edmund Husserl and Jacob Klein*, Indiana University Press, Bloomington and Indianapolis, 2011.
- ²⁴ See GMOA, 184: «From now on the fundamental ontological science of ancients is replaced by a symbolic discipline whose ontological presuppositions are left unclarified». In addition to this see GMOA, 192.
- ²⁵ See J. Klein, *The World of Physics and the 'Natural' World*, in LE, 33.
- ²⁶ About this see *Ausgewählte Briefe von Jacob Klein an Gerhard Krüger. 1929-1933* (= BKK), hrsg. Von E. Patard, in *New Yearbook for Phenomenology and Phenomenological Philosophy*, 1 (6), 2006, pp. 308-329: 328
- ²⁷ BKK, 329.